

REACTIVE POWER. REACTIVE POWER COMPENSATION.

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Abstract: It is possible to economically save electricity by compensating reactive energy in electric motors. Below we will consider the power of the capacitor device to compensate the reactive power through the simplest calculations.

Key words: reactive energy, active energy, power coefficient, full energy.

Reactive energy is a concept unknown to many, but it can be of great interest. Especially if you are looking to save money on your home or office electricity bill. In fact, you've seen it reflected in your energy bill and ignored it. Total energy is the sum of two energies, or in other words, it can be divided into two different types of energy:

- Active energy: this is what is actually converted into work (or heat). That is, what machines actually use and stay connected to the network. For example, a person who consumes stoves, lamps, televisions, household appliances, etc. It is measured in kWh.
- Reactive energy: This other imaginary energy is not put to practical use. In this case, it is measured in kVAr (kilovolt-ampere reactive per hour). This is related to devices that use spirals, such as industrial machines, fluorescent tubes, pumps, electric motors, etc.

Because of this, power companies must invest more in generation equipment and lines with larger distribution capacity, as well as transformers to transport and transform this reactive energy. All these costs are also calculated for reactive power.

Reactive power is used to create an electromagnetic field in electric motors, transformers, and power lines without performing useful work in electrical receivers.

Economical use of all types of energy, including electricity, issues of improving the efficiency of electrical devices are important. In recent years, a lot of attention has been paid to improving the quality of electricity. The quality of electricity can significantly affect the consumption of electricity, the reliability of power supply systems and the technological process of production. Rational reactive power compensation reduces energy losses due to reactive power flows, ensures the quality of consumed electricity by regulating and stabilizing the voltage level in power networks, and achieves high technical and economic performance of electrical devices.

The problem of reactive power compensation in the country's electrical systems is of great importance for the following reasons: 1) the consumption of reactive power compared to active power in industrial production has increased significantly; 2) consumption of reactive power in city power networks has increased due to the increase in household loads; 3) reactive power consumption in agricultural power networks is increasing. Currently, due to the increasing demand for electricity, we can save electricity by compensating reactive energy. Calculation of the capacity of the capacitor device to compensate the reactive power of the electric motor. The majority of the electricity produced in our country is due to pumping stations, power transmission lines, distribution devices, and electric motors. There are several ways to compensate reactive power. - by using capacitor devices, - synchronous generator devices, - synchronous compensators. Necessary formulas for calculating the capacity of the condenser device to compensate the reactive energy of electric motors in pumping stations, production facilities and similar facilities. (1), (2), (3), (4), (5)

$Q = Pa \cdot K$ (1) $Q = Pa \cdot (tg\varphi_{initial} - tg\varphi)$ (2) $Pa = S \cdot \cos\varphi_{initial}$ (3) $tg\varphi_{initial} = \sin\varphi_{initial} / \cos\varphi_{initial}$ (4) $tg\varphi = \sin\varphi / \cos\varphi$ (5) Here, Pa is the active power (watt), K is the coefficient from the table, S is the total power (kVA), Q is the reactive power (kVAR), $\cos\varphi$ is the power factor.

Installation of its calculated 1 reactive power compensating devices for each individual consumer frees electric power supply networks from excessive reactive power loading and provides maximum economic efficiency.

The installation of capacitor banks calculated for several groups of consumers leads to efficient use of these capacitors. Centralized compensation is carried out by connecting capacitor banks (3) to the voltage buses of the secondary winding of the transformer substation, so that the reactive power in the transformers and supply lines is relieved of loading. However, the secondary voltages of the substation are not free from reactive power loading. Also, while the battery of capacitors connected to the primary voltage side of the substation and the external power grid are freed from the reactive power load, they are not freed from these loads on the secondary voltage side and the consumers connected to it.

The purpose of using controlled capacitor batteries is not only to compensate reactive power, but also to maintain the set value of the voltage transmitted from the network during maximum and minimum loads without changing. We will use the information given to us initially to calculate the power of the

capacitor for reactive power compensation. If active power is not supplied, calculate full power S and power factor $\cos\phi$ by formula (3)- we calculate. $P_a = S \cdot \cos\phi$ (3) Then the required $\cos\phi_{talab}$ q from the table. and we find the coefficient K using the initial, i.e. $\cos\phi_{dastlabki}$ values in the passport of the electric motor and calculate it by the formula (1). $Q = P_a K$ (1) method: If active power is not provided, full power S and power coefficient $\cos\phi_{talab}$ q . by formula (3)- we calculate. $P_a = S \cdot \cos\phi_{dastlabki}$ (3) Then the power coefficients $\cos\phi_{dastlabki}$ and $\cos\phi_{talab}$ q . $tg\phi_{dastlabki}$ and $tg\phi_{talab}$ q using (4) and (5) - we calculate it and from formula (2) - we calculate the capacity of the condenser device for reactive power compensation. $Q = P_a \cdot (tg\phi_{dastlabki} - tg\phi_{talab}$ $q.)$ (2) For practical calculation: Active power of the electric motor $P_a = 200$ kW, Power coefficient $\cos\phi_{dastlabki} = 0.6$. We calculate the power of the capacitor to compensate the reactive power. In order to compensate the reactive power, we need to increase the value of $\cos\phi_{dastlabki}$, that is, we take $\cos\phi_{talab}$ $q = 0.9$. - we find the coefficient K from the table. $K = 0.85$ $Q = P_a \cdot K = 200 \times 0.85 = 170$ kVAR So, to compensate the reactive power of the electric motor, we install a capacitor device with a capacity of $Q = 170$ kVAR. The active power consumed by active power consumers of electric energy performs work and is transformed into other types of energy: mechanical, heat, light, chemical, compressed air energy, and gas. The reactive power produced in power plants is not enough, therefore, 2/3 of the reactive power needed by consumers is obtained with the help of compensating devices, and 1/3 from electric networks.

As a result of reactive power consumption, a rotating magnetic current is generated in an asynchronous motor, and with the help of this current, the required amount of active power is transferred from the stator to the rotor. Therefore, there are negative effects of reactive power consumption:

- The capacity of transformers and lines with additional load decreases;
- Power and energy losses in electric networks increase when supplying power to consumers.

A technical disadvantage in the use of capacitor batteries for reactive power compensation. The use of capacitor batteries for compensation is especially widely used. It is firmly stated that their compatibility with high and low voltages, small active power consumption (0.0025-0.005kW/kVar), the lowest comparative price (for 1kVar), simple operation; simple production assembly; suitability for installation in any dry buildings is their biggest advantage.

References:

1. "Guidelines for the design of reactive power compensation in power networks of industrial enterprises" Zhelezko Yu.S.
2. "Automatic devices for reactive power compensation in power networks of enterprises" Krasnik V.V.
3. Steven W. Blume, Electric power system basics, USA, 2007.
4. Karimov R.Ch., Rafikova G.R. Basics of electrical safety. Study guide. -T.: Spectrum Media Group. 2015.
5. Rules of safety techniques in the operation of electrical devices. "Uzdavenergonazorat" state inspection on control in electric energy. - T.: Work. 2016.